

Nanoscale Mechanics of the Tectorial Membrane are Determined by its Poroelasticity

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(Dated: 17 August 2024)

ABSTRACT

Because of its strategic position overlying the sensory receptor cells in the inner ear, the tectorial membrane (TM) is widely believed to play an important role in cochlear mechanics. However, the nature of this role is not well understood. Measurements of TMs that have been isolated from surrounding tissue demonstrate both viscous and elastic properties that are important at audio frequencies (Ghaffari *et al.*, 2010). More recent results demonstrate a striking dependence on the size of the mechanical probe used to make the measurement (Sellon *et al.*, 2019). To better understand implications of these results for cochlear mechanics, we analyzed a simple model of the interaction of outer hair cells and the overlying TM. Results suggest that the TM exerts both viscous and elastic forces on hair bundles that are “embedded” in the TM. As a result, embedded hair bundles can act as displacement detectors at low and high frequencies, but as velocity detectors at intermediate frequencies. The phase lead can be as much as a quarter of a cycle and could thereby affect the stability of micromechanical feedback paths that are thought to increase the sensitivity of hearing.

BACKGROUND

Models of hair bundle excitation. The mechanically sensitive hair bundles of hair cells are stimulated by relative motions of the reticular lamina and the overlying TM. Scanning electron microscopy studies have revealed imprints of the tallest row of OHC stereocilia on the undersurface of the TM (Figure 1). This observation supports the idea that the tips of OHC hair cell stereocilia are mechanically anchored to the TM and thereby constrained to move in proportion to shearing *displacements* of the TM relative to the reticular lamina.

However, the TM is 97% water by weight, and interactions of interstitial fluid with the TM’s elastic matrix are likely to play a key role in hair cell stimulation. The TM is a polyelectrolyte gel (Freeman *et al.*, 2003) that consists of a matrix of proteins and sugar groups that account for only 3% of the TM volume. The remaining 97% of the TM volume is water and small solutes including ions. The predominantly negative fixed charge on TM macromolecules attracts and concentrates mobile counterions from the bath. The concentration of mobile counterions increases the osmotic pressure in the gel and thereby attracts water. The resulting influx of water causes the gel to swell until further swelling is resisted by stress exerted on TM macromolecules. Thus, a gel consists of two phases – liquid and solid –

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FIGURE 1. Left: Scanning electron micrograph of the undersurface of the TM, showing imprints of the tallest row of OHC stereocilia. Adapted from Andrade et al. (2016). **Center:** Model of an OHC hair bundle with tip embedded in the TM. Radial displacements of the TM relative to the reticular lamina cause proportional angular displacements of the OHC hair bundle. Thus, bundle rotation is proportional to TM *displacement*. **Right:** Model of a hair bundle that is not embedded in the TM. Radial displacements of the TM relative to the reticular lamina excite fluid motions that generate torque on the hair bundle that is proportional to fluid velocity (not fluid displacement). As a result, bundle rotation is proportional to TM *velocity*.

and interactions between these phases can lead to behaviors that are different from those of viscoelastic solids. We refer to such behaviors as poroelastic.

Nanoscale mechanics of the TM. To characterize TM dynamics at the level of single hair bundles, the TMs of mice were isolated from the surrounding tissue and attached with a tissue adhesive (Cell-Tak) to a small rectangle of glass cut from a coverslip. A small microsphere (radius $R = 0.75 - 7.5 \mu\text{m}$) attached to an AFM cantilever was brought into contact with the TM and then indented into the TM using a piezoelectric crystal (Figure 2, left). A static displacement (δ_0) was applied to the cantilever, and then nanometer displacements were added to generate nano-indentations ($\delta \sim \pm 10 \text{ nm}$) at audio frequencies (0.1-3 kHz) (Figure 2, right).

FIGURE 2. Left: Schematic drawing depicting dynamic nanoscale indentations of the TM. **Right:** Schematic illustration of the indentation pattern, which consists of an initial preindentation ($\delta_0 = 0.1-0.4 \mu\text{m}$) followed by superimposed displacement steps at pseudo-random times (bottom trace). The resulting force on the probe (top trace) was determined from bending of the cantilever. Adapted from Sellon et al. (2019).

Dynamic modulus of the TM. Results of the experiment described in the previous section were analyzed to determine the magnitude and phase of the dynamic modulus E^* as follows. The pseudo-random time waveforms for force and displacement (Figure 2) were converted to functions of frequency using Fourier transforms. The dynamic modulus E^* was then determined by computing the ratio of the Fourier transform of force divided by the Fourier transform of displacement. A representative result is shown in Figure 3. The real part of $E^*(f)$ is proportional to stiffness at frequency f , and the imaginary part of $E^*(f)$ is proportional to viscosity at frequency f . The magnitude of the dynamic modulus $|E^*|$ tends to increase with frequency, from a few mN/m at a frequency of 1 Hz to a bit less than 100 mN/m at 1 kHz. At both low and high frequencies, the phase of E^* is small ($\sim 20^\circ$). However, at intermediate frequencies, the phase of E^* increases to a peak near 80° .

FIGURE 3. Measured values of the dynamic modulus $|E^*|$ for a representative apical segment of a mouse TM. The top and bottom panels show the magnitude and phase of the dynamic modulus from a typical experiment. Adapted from Sellon et al. (2019).

MODELING TM MECHANICS

Material Properties of the TM. Unlike previous measurements that have demonstrated viscoelastic properties of the TM (Ghaffari *et al.*, 2010, Gu *et al.*, 2008), nanoscale measurements exhibit a distinct phase lead over a limited range of frequencies. The form of this dependence suggests that it arises from the interaction of fluid (endolymph) with a gelatinous matrix (as shown in Sellon et al., 2014) in combination with a fibrillar network of collagen (as shown in Masaki et al., 2009). Such an interaction of a gelatinous matrix and fibrillar network of collagen has previously been shown to account for an analogous phase lead in cartilage (Nia *et al.*, 2011).

Structure of TM Material Properties. The combination of gelatinous matrix and fibrillar network of collagen can be represented as illustrated in Figure 4. This model highlights two important spatial scales. The smaller scale represents the effective size of pores through which endolymph permeates the gelatinous matrix of glycosaminoglycans that constitutes the bulk of the TM. By adding polyethylene glycols of varying molecular mass to the fluid that bathes the TM, the size of such pores has been estimated to be on the order of 10-20 nm (Sellon *et al.*, 2014). The larger spatial scale represents the spacing of collagen fibrils, which can be greater than 100 nm (Andrade *et al.*, 2016). Interactions of mechanisms at these different spatial scales determine the frequency dependence of the TM material.

FIGURE 4. Model of TM structure. The red grid represents the nonfibrillar matrix of glycosaminoglycans and associated interstitial fluid (endolymph) that gives rise to the poroelastic behavior expected for a polyelectrolyte gel. The blue springs represent collagen fibers. The black dot represents the point of mechanical excitation.

Frequency Dependence. The combination of a gelatinous matrix and fibrillar network can be understood to produce the distinct phase lead seen in the dynamic modulus as follows. At low frequencies, relative motions of the tips of hair bundles and the overlying TM are dominated by elastic forces that arise within both the nonfibrillar, gelatinous matrix and the fibrillar network of collagen. At higher frequencies, the importance of viscous forces, which primarily arise from the flow of fluid through the porous matrix, increases, since such fluid forces increase with velocity. Thus, there is transition from forces that are in-phase with TM displacement at low frequencies to forces that are in-phase with TM velocity at higher frequencies. At even higher frequencies, viscous forces in the matrix are large and there is little

deformation of the gelatinous matrix. At these asymptotically high frequencies, motions of the tips of hair bundles are resisted exclusively by the stiffness of the collagen fibers.

Lumped Element Model of TM. The frequency relations described in the previous section are consistent with the mechanical topology shown in Figure 5. The network of collagen fibrils is characterized by its stiffness k_a , and the porous matrix is characterized by its equilibrium stiffness k_b and viscous damping b . Notice however, that unlike ideal springs and dashpots, the elements in this model are not linear.

Because the force generated by a dashpot is proportional to frequency, the dashpot b generates little force at low frequencies. In this condition, we can remove the dashpot from the model. At low frequencies, the force f is then resisted by the series combination of k_a and k_b .

At high frequencies, the force generated by the dashpot is large and the displacement across the dashpot is therefore small. Thus the displacements y and w are nearly equal, and the force f is resisted by k_a alone. Because k_a is greater than or equal to the series combination of k_a with k_b , it follows that the high-frequency magnitude of k^* is greater than it is at low frequencies.

FIGURE 5. Schematic representation of the dynamic modulus E^* . **Left:** Material properties of the TM are approximated by a lumped element model in which k_b represents the equilibrium stiffness of the gelatinous matrix, b represents viscous damping due to the flow of endolymph through the matrix, and k_a represents the stiffness of collagen fibrils. Application of force f causes a local indentation of the TM (y), a part of which also compresses the collagen network a distance w . **Right:** The magnitude of the dynamic stiffness $|k^*|$ of the lumped element model is constant ($k_a k_b / (k_a + k_b)$) at low frequencies, and constant (k_a) at high frequencies, but it increases with frequency at intermediate frequencies (between $\omega = k_b/b$ and $\omega = (k_a + k_b)/b$, where ω represents radian frequency).

Lumped Element Model of Hair-Bundle Excitation. Figure 6 incorporates the lumped element model of the TM from Figure 5 with a rigid-body model of hair-bundle excitation.

FIGURE 6. Model of hair bundle excitation by a poroelastic TM. **Left:** Schematic representation of the hair bundle rotation caused by shearing motion of the TM. The hair bundle is represented by a rigid cylinder that is attached by a spring-loaded (k_c) hinge to a rigid plate that represents the reticular lamina. The TM is represented by a rigid plate that overlies but does not touch the rigid cylinder. Displacement X_T of the upper plate transmits a force through the lumped element model and thereby causes a displacement X_B of the tip of the rotating cylinder. **Right:** Magnitude of the transfer function that relates shearing displacement X_T of the TM to displacement X_B of the hair bundle. As with the driving point stiffness (Figure 5), the magnitude of the transfer function tends to plateau at both low and high frequencies, but increases with frequency for a band of intermediate frequencies.

Functional Significance of Phase Lead. While there is considerable uncertainty about the details, it is widely believed that OHCs participate in a feedback system that ultimately leads to cochlear amplification (Figure 7). Some of the major steps in such a feedback process introduce delay so that their outputs tend to lag their inputs. For example,

OHC mechano-electric processes are thought to introduce capacitive delays associated with the transformation of receptor current to receptor voltage. Excessive delays in feedback paths can have detrimental effects on the response properties of feedback systems, and can even introduce instabilities. Our results suggest that nanoscale mechanics of the TM can introduce phase *leads* that could oppose otherwise detrimental delay mechanisms.

FIGURE 7. Simplified view of cochlear feedback from the perspective of a single OHC. Displacement x_b of the OHC hair bundle is stimulated by nanomechanical processes driven by shearing displacements of the TM relative to the reticular lamina. OHC mechano-electric processes transform bundle displacement x_b to a receptor potential v_m and electro-mechanical processes transform v_m to a change in OHC length Δl . Feedback results when the OHC length change Δl alters the nanomechanical relation between the TM and hair bundle and thereby alters x_b .

CONCLUSIONS

Our measurements demonstrate a characteristic frequency dependence in which forces are in phase with displacement at both low and high frequencies, but are in phase with TM velocity at transition frequencies. The phase lead can be as much as a quarter of a cycle. This frequency dependence is quite different from that of a viscoelastic solid, and is quite different from those measured in TMs using larger probes.

The frequency dependence of the driving-point dynamic stiffness of the TM and of the resulting micromechanical transfer function are consistent with a multi-component model of the TM. A nonfibrillar matrix of glycosaminoglycans and associated interstitial fluid (endolymph) give rise to poroelastic behaviors expected for a polyelectrolyte gel. This gel is supported in part by the fibrillar structure of collagen, which generates an additional stiffness component.

Differences between poroelastic and viscoelastic responses may directly affect the stability of micromechanical feedback paths and ultimately the sensitivity of hearing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the National Institutes of Health Grant R01-DC00238, and F32-CA216944-01, and by the National Science Foundation Grant CMMI-1536233 and a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant 1122374.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[George Burwood]: The reported phase transition at intermediate frequencies is certainly an interesting observation and could explain a lot about how the TM contributes to tuning relatively broad reticular lamina responses. However, I am hesitant to agree that the phase transition is direct evidence for a tuning mechanism, purely because there is no discussion in the paper of where along the tonotopic axis the example TM piece was derived from, and no attempt to test whether the frequencies used to derive the modulus and phase were relevant to the characteristic frequency of the TM piece. If you were to test an apical piece and a basal piece using this same frequency range, might the phase transition be absent from the basal piece, or do the frequency tuning properties of the TM depend upon the tonotopic context of the underlying organ of Corti? I am looking forward to seeing the poster for more information! It would be helpful to comment in the manuscript upon the relationship between your idea, the tested frequency range, and the TM's tonotopic properties.

[Dennis Freeman]: The example in Figure 3 shows results for an apical segment of the TM of a mouse. We have made a few measurements of TMs from different cochlear regions, and we have seen significant differences – especially in the magnitude of E^* . Interestingly, we have seen very large phase differences when we varied the size of the probe. Therefore, even small differences in the morphology of a hair bundle as a function of longitudinal distance could in theory produce large differences in the frequency of the peak phase.

According to linear poroelastic theory, the frequency of maximum phase is given by

$$f_{peak} \propto \frac{kE}{d^2}$$

where k represents the hydraulic permeability, E represents the equilibrium modulus, and d represents the distance over which the probe is in contact with the TM (see illustration in Figure 2). We verified this relation by comparing results for microspheres with different radii. When we increased the radius of the microsphere by a factor of 10, the peak frequency decreased by more than a factor of 100. If we decreased the size of the probe by a factor of 10 (so that the probe diameter is similar to the diameter of a single stereocilium), we would expect the frequency of the peak phase to increase by a factor of 100 – thereby reaching tens of kilohertz. Unfortunately, we have not been able to try small probes because of frequency limitations of our current measurement system. We are developing a closely related measurement system using Laser Doppler Vibrometry instead of AFM as the detector. This new system should allow measurements across the audio frequency range.

[Patricia M. Quinones]: Interesting poster. In your experiment, it seems that the applied step is in the "up-down" direction of the TM (Fig. 2, left). If the sphere represents the bundle-tip, wouldn't the motion be in the "left-right" direction? If so, does this make a difference for the results given the TM fiber-orientation?

[Dennis Freeman]: You are correct that we measured motions in the vertical (transverse) direction. We focused on transverse measurements because they could be done with commercially available AFM probes (which are designed to measure in the transverse direction). Measurements based on radial motions would be more relevant to hearing, and we are working on probes of custom design to support such measurements.

Previous measurements suggest that the radial impedance of the TM exceeds that in the longitudinal direction by a factor of 2 to 3 (Gu *et al.*, 2008, Abnet and Freeman, 2000). Differences between longitudinal and transverse impedances are likely to be smaller since the primary anisotropy results from the radial disposition of collagen fibrils. Of course, these previous measurements were made with much larger probes than were used in the present study.